

CARBON CREDITS AND JSC “UZBEKHYDROENERGO”: TRANSFORMATION TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: The article explores the concept of carbon credits and their potential role in the sustainable development strategy of “Uzbekhydroenergo” JSC. In response to increasing global pressure to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, carbon offsets have emerged as a crucial environmental tool for neutralizing ecological impacts. Carbon offsets involve projects that reduce or prevent emissions, with one carbon unit equating to one metric ton of CO₂ or equivalent gases. The article highlights the importance of certification organizations like Verra and Gold Standard in ensuring the credibility of these projects. It discusses major corporations such as Shell and Volkswagen as significant users of carbon offsets, and examines popular offset projects including renewable energy, reforestation, and carbon capture. The article emphasizes Uzbekhydroenergo’s unique position in Uzbekistan’s renewable energy sector, suggesting that the company can capitalize on carbon offset projects by modernizing hydroelectric plants and restoring ecosystems. By leveraging international experience and selling certified offsets, “Uzbekhydroenergo” could strengthen its global market position and contribute to Uzbekistan’s sustainable development.

Keywords: Carbon credits, sustainable development, greenhouse gas emissions, hydroelectric power plants, renewable energy, CO₂, environmental initiatives, certification, verification, Paris Agreement, global climate change, reforestation, energy efficiency, carbon neutrality.

KARBON KOMPENSATSIYALARI VA “O‘ZBEKGIDROENERGO” AJ: BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH O‘ZGARISHLARI

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“O‘zbekgidroenergo” AJ

Transformatsiyani amalga oshirish,
yashil iqtisodiyot va ESG tamoyillarini joriy
qilish ofisi boshlig‘i

Annotatsiya: Maqolada karbon kompensatsiyalari konsepsiyasi va uning “O‘zbekgidroenergo” AJ faoliyatidagi ahamiyati tahliliy yoritiladi. Karbon kompensatsiyalari global iqlim o‘zgarishi sharoitida issiqxona gazlari chiqindilarini neytrallashtirish vositasi sifatida ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, karbon kompensatsiyalari qanday ishlashi, ularni sertifikatlash jarayonida Verra va Gold Standard kabi tashkilotlarning roli hamda qayta tiklanadigan energiya, o‘rmonlarni qayta tiklash va energiya samaradorligini oshirish kabi mashhur karbon kompensatsiya loyihalari tahlil qilinadi. “O‘zbekgidroenergo” AJning

КАРБОНОВЫЕ КОМПЕНСАЦИИ И АО «УЗБЕКГИДРОЭНЕРГО»: ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ РАЗВИТИЮ

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Аннотация: В статье анализируются углеродные компенсации и их значение в деятельности АО «Узбекгидроэнерго». Компенсация выбросов представляется как один из способов нейтрализации парниковых газов в условиях глобальных климатических изменений. Анализируются механизмы работы углеродных компенсаций, роль сертифицирующих организаций, таких как Verra и Gold Standard, а также популярные проекты в этой сфере, включая возобновляемые источники энергии, лесовосстановление и повышение энергоэффективности. Рассмотрены возможности и перспективы АО «Узбекгидроэнерго» по участию в проектах по компенсации выбросов

karbon kompensatsiya loyihalarida ishtirok etishdagi imkoniyatlari va istiqbollari ko'rib chiqiladi, jumladan, gidroelektr stansiyalarni modernizatsiya qilish va yangi obyektlar qurish orqali Jamiyatning barqaror rivojlanishga hissa qo'shish imkoniyatlari muhokama qilinadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, maqolada karbon kompensatsiyalari orqali "O'zbekgidroenergo" AJning jahon bozorida o'rnini mustahkamlash va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish bo'yicha global sa'y-harakatlarga qo'shilishi mumkinligi qayd etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: karbon kompensatsiyalari, barqaror rivojlanish, issiqxona gazlari, gidroelektr stansiya, qayta tiklanadigan energiya, CO₂, ekologik tashabbuslar, sertifikatatsiya, verifikatsiya, Parij kelishuvi, global iqlim o'zgarishi, o'rmonlarni tiklash, energiya samaradorligi, uglerod neytralligi.

углерода, в том числе возможности внести свой вклад в устойчивое развитие Общества путем модернизации гидроэлектростанций и строительства новых объектов. Кроме того, подчеркивается, что использование углеродных компенсаций может помочь укрепить позиции Узбекгидроэнерго на международном рынке и внести вклад в глобальные экологические инициативы.

Ключевые слова: Карбоновые компенсации, устойчивое развитие, парниковые газы, гидроэлектростанции, возобновляемая энергия, CO₂, экологические инициативы, сертификация, верификация, Парижское соглашение, глобальное изменение климата, лесовосстановление, энергоэффективность, углеродная нейтральность.

In the context of global climate change, governments around the world are increasing pressure on the private sector to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In response, global corporations implemented carbon offsets – an environmental tool that helps neutralize their ecological impact.

Carbon offsetting is a process or project aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions in one area to compensate for emissions produced in another area. One carbon or offset unit is equivalent to one metric ton of carbon dioxide or other greenhouse gases. Companies and individuals can invest in emission reduction projects to offset their own CO₂ emissions resulting from industrial production, transportation, or other activities. The main goal of carbon offsets is to neutralize greenhouse gas emissions to mitigate the effects of global warming.

How Do Carbon Offsets Work?

Carbon offsets involve the implementation of projects that directly reduce or prevent greenhouse gas emissions. This can include planting trees, developing renewable energy sources, or improving energy efficiency. Companies looking to offset their emissions invest in such projects, receiving in return certified carbon offsets that verify the reduction in emissions.

Role of Certification Organizations. Organizations like Verra and Gold Standard play a key role in certifying and verifying carbon offsets. They ensure transparency, accountability, and high quality of offset projects worldwide. These organizations establish strict standards and verification procedures, making offsets certified by them highly valued in the global market.

Major Users of Carbon Offsets. In 2023, major users of carbon offsets included large corporations such as Shell, Volkswagen, and Yamato. These companies aim to achieve carbon neutrality by complying with CO₂ emission regulations set by legislation.

Popular Carbon Offset Projects

Renewable Energy: Construction of wind and solar power plants, as well as hydroelectric power stations.

Reforestation: Planting trees and restoring forests that absorb CO₂.

Energy Efficiency: Upgrading equipment and technologies to reduce energy consumption.

Carbon Capture and Storage: Technologies that capture and store carbon emissions from industrial processes.

“Uzbekhydroenergo” JSC and Carbon Offsets

“Uzbekhydroenergo” JSC, as a leader in renewable energy production in Uzbekistan, has unique opportunities to participate in carbon offset projects. Hydroelectric power plants, which produce electricity without direct CO₂ emissions, can form the basis for projects that offset carbon emissions. Such projects can include the modernization of existing hydroelectric plants or the construction of new facilities, as well as the development of related environmental initiatives such as the restoration of water bodies and ecosystems.

Prospects and Benefits. Uzbekhydroenergo JSC can leverage the experience of other countries where renewable energy and carbon offset projects have been successfully implemented. Adapting best practices will allow the company to become a significant player in the carbon offset market. The company can also consider selling certified carbon offsets to other countries, especially those with emission reduction commitments under international agreements like the Paris Agreement. This can become an important source of revenue and contribute to the sustainable development of Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

Carbon offsets are an important tool in combating climate change, and they can play a key role in Uzbekhydroenergo JSC’s strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and achieve sustainable development. Implementing such projects will help the company strengthen its position in the global market and make a significant contribution to global environmental protection efforts.

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